

Communication from the faith

By: Abel Suing arsuing@utpl.edu.ec

The pilgrimage of the Virgin Mary, in the invocation of El Cisne, is a tradition and identity of the Ecuadorians. It is celebrated between 17 and 20 August, from El Cisne to Loja, and initiates a period of commemoration around the Nativity of Our Lady which occurs on 8 September, according to the calendar of the Christian saints.

Fidelity and trust motivate a model of communication in Catholic practice. On the day of the pilgrimage, the media and social networks transmit messages of love in plural formats, popular voices and expressions multiplied in expanded and transmedia narratives. Thus, the community appropriates technologies to recognize each other and maintain ties, regardless of where they live, in a region characterized by historical and massive migratory movements.

But there are also people of different socio-economic profiles, geographical origins, ages, genders, occupations and a host of other characteristics that coincide in their rights, and also in freedom of thought because the Catholic faith is part of the forms, signs and essence of being Ecuadorian.

Both victims and perpetrators turn to Mary in search of peace. Those who recognize their faults, perhaps aspire to make amends, and seek to integrate in order to achieve redemption. There is thus a space for dialogue, for communication mediated by values and culture.

Other institutions have failed to pacify Ecuador and achieve sustainable progress. It could be that the talks originating in and from faith, around families, hold the keys to safeguarding the lives of those who live in this region of Latin America.